

Actual vs Predicted (SunHoursVariance)

Standardized Residuals (SunHoursVariance)

Partial Regression Plot (SunHoursVariance)

Durbin-Watson Statistic

$$DW = 1.2567$$

Interpretation:

1 = positive autocorrelation

2 = no autocorrelation

4 = negative autocorrelation

Breusch–Pagan Test

LM Statistic: 1.0476

p-value: 0.3061

Conclusion: No Heteroskedasticity

White Test

White Statistic: 1.0500

df: 2

p-value: 0.5916

Conclusion: No Heteroskedasticity

Histogram of Residuals (SunHoursVariance)

P-P Plot (Normality Test) – SunHoursVariance

